

ISic4337

I.Sicily inscription 4337

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Comiso

Provenance

contrada Cifali

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Kamarina, Museo Archeologico
Regionale di Kamarina

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

Di Stefano, G. 2013. Kamarina. Le acquisizioni, il museo tematico, la collezione "Biagio Pace", il lapidario. Ispica. At 32 ph

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